

Derivation of expected utility function

Assuming that the difference between means follows a normal distribution, $\bar{X} \sim N(\theta, \tau^2/n)$, and the unknown parameter also follows a normal distribution, $\theta \sim N(\mu_0, \sigma_0^2)$. The optimal utility is

$$G(n, \theta) = (\theta - c_2)(N - n/\rho)I_{\{\bar{x} > z_\alpha \tau / \sqrt{n}\}} + \frac{n}{2}(\theta - c_2) - c_1 n - c_f I_{\{n > 0\}}.$$

The expectation of the utility is the expectation taken over the posterior distribution of θ for all possible values of responses, \bar{X} . However, as \bar{X} is unknown at the planning stage the expected utility of the optimal decision is obtained from the distribution of \bar{X} given θ and n . As θ is unknown, the expectation of the expected utility is taken over the prior distribution of θ ,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{G}(n, z_\alpha) \\ &= \iint [(\theta - c_2)(N - n/\rho)I_{\{\bar{x} \geq z_\alpha \tau / \sqrt{n}\}} + (\theta - c_2)\frac{n}{2} \\ & \quad - c_1 n - c_f I_{\{n > 0\}}] f(\theta|\bar{x})f(\bar{x}|n) d\bar{x} d\theta \\ &= (N - n) \int_{z_\alpha \tau / \sqrt{n}}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \theta f(\theta|\bar{x})f(\bar{x}|n) d\theta d\bar{x} \\ & \quad - c_2 \Phi(-Z)(N - n/\rho) + \frac{n}{2}(\mu_0 - c_2) - c_1 n \\ & \quad - c_f I_{\{n > 0\}} \\ &= (N - n/\rho) \left\{ (\mu_0 - c_2)\Phi(-Z) + \frac{\sigma_0^2}{\sigma_x} \phi(Z) \right\} \\ & \quad + \frac{n}{2}(\mu_0 - c_2) - c_1 n - c_f I_{\{n > 0\}} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $f(\theta|\bar{x})$ is the posterior density of θ given \bar{x} , $f(\bar{x}|n)$ is the prior predictive density function of \bar{x} , $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the normal cumulative distribution function, $\phi(\cdot)$ is the normal density function, $Z = \frac{z_\alpha \tau / \sqrt{n} - \mu_0}{\sigma_x}$ and $\sigma_x^2 = \sigma_0^2 + \tau^2/n$. The expected utility is a function of n and z_α .